

Synthesis and characterization of some mixed ligand complexes of chromium(III)

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The preparation and characterization of some new chromium(III) complexes, synthesized by the reactions of different chromium salts with 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol (L), neutral bidentate Schiff bases *N,N'*-ethylenebis(benzophenoneimine) (L¹), *N,N'*-ethylenebis-(acetophenoneimine) (L²) and *N*-phenyl-2-(2-acetylpyridyl)imine (L³) under varied reaction conditions are reported. The reactions of the isolated complex [Cr(L)₂(Py)Cl]Cl₂.H₂O with acetylacetone (Hacac), glycine (Hgly), *N*-phenylsalicylaldehyde (Hsalan) and *N*-phenyl-ortho-hydroxyacetophenoneimine (Hohapan) yield heterochelates of the type [Cr(L)₂(lig)]Cl₂.H₂O (where lig = mono anion of Hacac, Hgly, Hsalan or Hohapan). The stereochemistry of the isolated complexes has been discussed.

Chromium(III) complexes of mixed-ligands and macrocycles are of much importance^{1,2}. Kinetics and mechanism of ligand exchange reactions of such complexes of chromium(III) have some biological significance³. Besides, chromium has been considered to be an essential trace element in experimental animals and probably in man, where chromium is present in the trivalent state⁴. Of interest is the fact that chromium(III) biologically acts as a cofactor in the initiation of insulin action; chromium(III) can form a ternary complex between insulin-S and tissue insulin receptor-SH, facilitating the initial insulin-tissue interaction. The hypothetical chromium(III) complexes occurring in brewers' yeast and other foods, termed 'glucose tolerance factor', were found to be of outstanding biological activity⁵. However, the biologically active form of chromium is not well-defined yet. Therefore, a thorough knowledge of the coordination chemistry of chromium with mixed-ligands and macrocycles (involving different donor atoms) will be of much interest in elucidating the structure-reactivity correlation of the said complexes. For obvious reasons we initiated work in this direction and we described here the preparation, properties and characterization of some chromium(III) mixed-ligand complexes of the above type. The complexes were synthesized by the reactions of different chromium(III) salts with 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol (L), neutral bidentate Schiff bases *N,N'*-ethylenebis(benzophenoneimine) (L¹), *N,N'*-ethylenebis(acetophenoneimine) (L²) and *N*-phenyl-2-(2-acetylpyridyl)imine (L³) under varied reaction conditions. The reactions of the complex [Cr(L)₂(Py)Cl]Cl₂.H₂O with acetylacetone (Hacac), glycine (Hgly), *N*-phenylsalicylaldehyde (Hsalan) and *N*-phenyl-ortho-hydroxyacetophenoneimine (Hohapan) leading to the isolation of interesting heterochelates of chromium(III) are also included in this communication.

Results and Discussion

Reactions of different chromium(III) salts/complexes

with diamines and neutral bidentate Schiff bases under varied reaction conditions yielded varieties of new coloured mixed-ligand complexes of chromium(III) (1-20) (Table 1). The reactions of [Cr(L)₂PyCl]Cl₂.H₂O (13) with acetylacetone, glycine, *N*-phenylsalicylaldehyde and *N*-phenyl-ortho-hydroxyacetophenoneimine afforded heterochelates [Cr(L)₂(lig)]Cl₂.H₂O (21-24) respectively (where lig = monoanion of acetylacetone, glycine, *N*-phenylsalicylaldehyde and *N*-phenyl-ortho-hydroxyacetophenoneimine). The filtrate from 21 afforded another chromium(III) heterochelates [(acac)Cr(acacpnol)] (25) (where acacpnol is the dianion of the Schiff base derived from Hacac and L).

The elemental analyses, molar conductance values, magnetic moments, molecular weights of the complexes (Table 1) support the formulations of the isolated chelates.

The molar conductance (in DMSO) values (Table 1) of complexes 1, 5-8 are found in the range 50-60 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ suggesting 1 : 1 electrolytic nature⁶. On the other hand, complexes 3, 13, 21 and 22 show conductance values in the range 70-80 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ consistent with 1 : 2 electrolyte⁶. The rest of the complexes 2, 9-20 in the same solvent show the values in the range 90-100 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ which is quite consistent with 1 : 3 electrolytic nature of the complexes in the solution. Complex 23, however, show conductance value of 8.8 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ showing its non-conducting nature.

Complexes 1-10 show symmetric and asymmetric ν_{NH₂} modes in the region 2850-3195 cm⁻¹ (Refs. 2, 7, 8), while original diamines L and L¹ show these modes at 3300-3350 cm⁻¹. The change of shift towards the lower frequency suggests involvement of amino nitrogen in bond formation to chromium(III) ion in these chelates. This is further substantiated by the appearance of bands at 510-540 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{Cr-N} mode^{8,9}. The infrared spectra of complexes 5-8 show bands at ~2070 (s) (a doublet) and 760 (m) cm⁻¹ (a doublet) assignable to C≡N and C-S stretching

vibrations respectively^{9,10}. The bonding of thiocyanato group with chromium(III) ion occurs through nitrogen as evident from the band due to C-S stretching at 760 cm⁻¹. Based on the data available in literature, it may be concluded that the thiocyanato group coordinates through nitrogen for first row transition metal and through sulphur for the second row transition metals. The appearance of doublets (see above) may be taken as evidenced for the presence of ionic SCN⁻ in these complexes^{9,10}. The presence of Cr-N linkage in these complexes is further supported by the appearance of bands at ~530-585 cm⁻¹ in the far-infrared spectra of the complexes. Besides, the ionic nature of SCN⁻ in complexes 17-20 is also demonstrated by the appearance of the bands at 2050 (s) and 750 (m) cm⁻¹, which may be considered as CN stretching and CS stretching vibrations respectively^{9,10}. The NH stretching frequency¹¹ of NH₃ in complexes 17-20 occurs at 3000-3400 cm⁻¹. For complexes 21 and 25, the oxygen-bonded chelating acetylacetonate anion has been inferred from the vibrational spectra¹², despite the added complexities due to the C=N and C=C stretching modes of the H₂acacpnol ligand. Antisymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of COO⁻ observed at around 1600 and 1390 cm⁻¹ respectively, in complex 22 show the monobasic bidentate chelate nature of the glycinate anion¹³. The ν_{NH} was observed around 3340 cm⁻¹. However, the presence of lattice water complicates this interpretation. The presence of coordinated pyridine molecule in complexes 13-16 is supported by the appearance of ν_{CH} (aromatic) at ~3000 cm⁻¹ and ν_{C-C} (aromatic) and ν_{CN} (ring) at 1440-1590 cm⁻¹ (Ref. 14). The presence of anionic bidentate heteroligands in complexes 23 and 24 has been inferred from the interpretation of the infrared spectra of the free ligands and their metal complexes, and the aspect has been thoroughly discussed elsewhere¹³.

The electronic absorption spectra of some of the chromium(III) complexes in methanol were measured. Some of the chelates, when taken in nujol mull gave almost identical spectra, specially in the range 18000-25000 cm⁻¹. This suggests that the environment of chromium(III) is substantially the same in both solid and solution. Complexes 2-4, 6-8, 10-12, 14-16, 18-20 and 25 show three bands in the range 18180-20600 (shoulder), 22280-22122 (ε ~4000) and 25400-26900 cm⁻¹ (ε ~4200-6000), which may be attributed to the split-components of the ⁴T_{2g} (O_h) and ⁴T_{1g} (F) (O_h) terms despite their relatively high extinction coefficients. Similar high extinction coefficients were observed for band in this region in the chromium(III) complexes of *N*-substituted-salicylaldimines¹⁵, *N,N'*-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine)^{16,17} and *N,N'*-ethylenebis(acetylacetonateimine)¹⁷. The rest of the complexes, i.e. 1, 5, 9, 13, 17, 21-24 show three bands in the region 17000-16000 (ε ~50), 20000-19500 (ε ~80), 25000-24800 cm⁻¹ (ε ~125) suggesting pseudo-octahedral stereochemistry of the chromium(III) complexes under discussion¹⁸.

The room temperature magnetic moments are slightly

lower (Table 1) than the spin-only value for a d³-ion and this aspect has been thoroughly discussed¹⁵⁻¹⁹.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the chromium(III) complexes^a

Compd.	Analysis % :		μ _{eff} ^a B.M.	λ ₂ ^b Ω ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	Found/(Calcd.)	Cr		
[Cr(L) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O (1)	28.00	13.92	3.58	50.5
C ₆ H ₂₄ N ₄ Cl ₃ O ₄ Cr	(28.43)	(13.88)		
[Cr(L ¹) ₃]Cl ₃ .H ₂ O (2)	12.52	5.90	3.50	95.5
C ₄₈ H ₅₀ N ₆ Cl ₃ O ₂ Cr	(12.04)	(5.87)		
[Cr(L ²) ₂ (H ₂ O)Cl]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O (3)	14.50	6.99	3.79	70.5
C ₃₆ H ₄₈ N ₄ Cl ₃ O ₄ Cr	(14.04)	(6.85)		
[Cr(L ³) ₃]Cl ₃ .2H ₂ O (4)	13.71	6.74	3.90	98.0
C ₃₉ H ₄₃ N ₆ Cl ₃ O ₂ Cr	(13.61)	(6.64)		
[Cr(L) ₂ (NCS) ₂]NCS.5H ₂ O (5)	-	10.50	3.80	50.0
C ₉ H ₃₀ N ₇ O ₇ S ₃ Cr	(10.48)			
[Cr(L ¹) ₂ (NCS) ₂]NCS (6)	-	7.58	3.78	55.0
C ₃₅ H ₃₂ N ₇ S ₃ Cr	(7.44)			
[Cr(L ²) ₂ (NCS) ₂]NCS.H ₂ O (7)	-	6.82	3.98	56.8
C ₃₉ H ₄₂ N ₇ S ₃ O ₂ Cr	(6.73)			
[Cr(L ³) ₂ (NCS) ₂]NCS.2H ₂ O (8)	-	7.85	3.99	50.0
C ₂₉ H ₃₀ N ₇ S ₃ O ₂ Cr	(7.95)			
[Cr(L ₃)]Cl ₃ .H ₂ O (9)	23.68	11.69	3.88	96.2
C ₉ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₄ Cl ₃ Cr	(23.85)	(11.73)		
[Cr(L ¹) ₃]Cl ₃ .2H ₂ O (10)	11.98	5.68	3.87	98.5
C ₄₈ H ₅₂ N ₆ Cl ₃ O ₂ Cr	(11.80)	(5.76)		
[Cr(L ²) ₃]Cl ₃ (11)	11.82	5.72	3.88	97.0
C ₅₄ H ₆₀ N ₆ Cl ₃ Cr	(11.20)	(5.45)		
[Cr(L ³) ₃]Cl ₃ (12)	14.80	6.82	3.90	96.5
C ₃₉ H ₃₉ N ₆ Cl ₃ Cr	(14.26)	(6.96)		
[Cr(L) ₂ (Py)Cl]Cl ₂ .H ₂ O (13)	24.95	11.72	3.99	70.0
C ₁₁ H ₂₇ N ₅ Cl ₃ O ₃ Cr	(24.45)	(11.94)		
[Cr(L ¹) ₂ (Py) ₂]Cl ₃ (14)	13.30	6.79	3.98	97.8
C ₄₂ H ₄₂ N ₆ Cl ₃ Cr	(13.50)	(6.59)		
[Cr(L ²) ₂ (Py) ₂]Cl ₃ (15)	12.42	6.82	3.90	99.0
C ₄₆ H ₅₀ N ₆ Cl ₃ Cr	(12.61)	(6.15)		
[Cr(L ³) ₂ (Py) ₂]Cl ₃ (16)	15.28	7.93	3.74	95.5
C ₃₆ H ₃₆ N ₆ Cl ₃ Cr	(15.03)	(7.33)		
[Cr(L) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂](SCN) ₃ (17)	-	11.98	3.78	96.0
C ₉ H ₂₆ N ₉ S ₃ O ₂ Cr	(11.81)			
[Cr(L ¹) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂](SCN) ₃ (18)	-	7.80	3.80	97.8
C ₃₅ H ₃₈ N ₉ S ₃ Cr	(7.10)			
[Cr(L ²) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂](SCN) ₃ (19)	-	6.44	3.90	95.0
C ₃₉ H ₄₆ N ₉ S ₃ Cr	(6.59)			
[Cr(L ³) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂](SCN) ₃ (20)	-	8.00	3.98	95.8
C ₂₉ H ₃₂ N ₉ S ₃ Cr	(7.97)			
[Cr(L) ₂ (acac)]Cl ₂ .H ₂ O (21)	16.88	13.82	3.99	75.5
C ₁₁ H ₂₉ N ₄ Cl ₂ O ₅ Cr	(16.90)	(12.38)		
[Cr(L) ₂ (gly)Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O (22)	17.00	12.80	3.90	79.2
C ₈ H ₂₈ N ₅ Cl ₂ O ₆ Cr	(17.19)	(12.59)		
[Cr(L) ₂ (salan)]Cl ₂ .H ₂ O (23)	13.52	10.00	3.85	72.5
C ₁₉ H ₃₂ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₂ Cr	(13.73)	(10.13)		
[Cr(L) ₂ (ohapan)]Cl ₂ .H ₂ O (24)	13.82	9.92	3.89	76.8
C ₂₀ H ₃₄ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₂ Cr	(13.36)	(9.86)		
{(acacpnol)Cr(acac)} (25)	-	12.72	3.88	8.8
C ₁₈ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₅ Cr	(12.89)			

^a L = H₂NCH₂CH(OH)CH₂NH₂; L¹ = PhCH=NCH₂CH₂N=CHPh; L² = PhC(CH₃)=NCH₂CH₂N=(CH₃)CPh; L³ = C₅H₅N.C(CH₃)=NPh "Solid state at room temperature. ^b 10⁻³ M solution in DMSO at room temperature.

Experimental

The solvents and chemicals were purified and dried before use by standard techniques. The elemental analyses were carried out at the R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The electronic spectra (ethanol) were recorded on a Hitachi 200-20 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr/nujol/HCB) on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer. The molar conductance was measured using an Elico conductivity bridge. The magnetic susceptibility was determined by the Gouy method. Molecular weight was determined by Rast's method.

1,3-Diaminopropane-2-ol (L) (Aldrich) was used as such. The neutral Schiff bases derived from the condensation of ethylenediamine with benzaldehyde (L¹) and acetophenone (L²) and 2-acetylpyridine with aniline (L³) were prepared by published method²⁰.

[Cr(L)₂Cl₂]Cl₂.H₂O (1) : Ethanolic solution (40 cm³) of L (0.02 mol) was added to a solution of CrCl₃.6H₂O (0.01 mol) in the same solvent (50 cm³) and heated under gentle reflux for 30 min. The resulting bluish violet solution on concentration and cooling (~5°) yielded bluish violet solid. It was washed with cold ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl₂ (yield ~70%).

[Cr(L¹)₃]Cl₃.H₂O (2), [Cr(L²)₂(H₂O)Cl]Cl₂.3H₂O (3) and [Cr(L³)₃]Cl₃.2H₂O (4) : Similar reactions of CrCl₃.6H₂O with L¹, L² and L³ gave these three compounds in about 75% yield.

[Cr(L)₂(NCS)₂]NCS.5H₂O (5) : Potassium thiocyanate (0.03 mol) taken in ethanol (50 cm³) was added to a solution of Cr(NO₃)₃.9H₂O (0.01 mol) in the same solvent (50 cm³) and stirred thoroughly. The white precipitate of KNO₃ that separated out was filtered off and to the pink filtrate the diamine ligand L (0.02 mol) taken in ethanol (30 cm³) was added slowly with stirring. The resulting bluish solid was washed with ethanol and dried as above (yield ~65%).

[Cr(L¹)₂(NCS)₂]NCS (6), [Cr(L²)₂(NCS)₂]NCS.H₂O (7) and [Cr(L³)₂(NCS)₂]NCS.2H₂O (8) : Similarly as above these compounds were synthesized in about 70% yield.

[Cr(Lig)₃]Cl₃.H₂O (where Lig = L (9), Lig = L¹ (10), Lig = L² (11), Lig = L³ (12)) : Reaction of [Cr(urea)₆]Cl₃.3H₂O (0.001 mol) with L, L¹, L² or L³ (0.003 mol) in ethanol under reflux in presence of sodium acetate gave these compounds in about 70% yield.

[Cr(Lig)₂(Py)_nCl_m]Cl_z(H₂O)_z (where Lig = L, n = 1, m = 1, y = 2, z = 1 (13), Lig = L¹, n = 2, m = 0, y = 3, z = 0 (14), Lig = L², n = 2, m = 0, y = 3, z = 0 (15), Lig = L³, n = 2, m = 0, y = 3, z = 0 (16)) : A mixture of CrCl₃.6H₂O (0.01 mol) and Lig (0.02 mol) was added to freshly distilled pyridine (50 cm³) immediately followed by the addition of zinc dust (1 g) and reflux (30 min). It was then filtered and the brown filtrate yielded these compounds (yield ~65%).

[Cr(Lig)₂(NH₃)₂](SCN)₃ (where Lig = L (17), Lig = L¹ (18), Lig = L² (19), Lig = L³ (20)) : To NH₄[Cr(SCN)₄(NH₃)₂].H₂O (0.003 mol) dissolved in

ethanol (50 cm³) was added Lig (0.006 mol) in ethanol (50 cm³) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h and filtered. The brown filtrate gave these compounds in over 70% yield.

[Cr(L)₂(acac)]Cl₂.H₂O (21), [Cr(L)₂(gly)]Cl₂.H₂O (22), [Cr(L)₂(salam)]Cl₂.H₂O (23) and [Cr(L)₂(ohapan)]Cl₂.H₂O (24) : These brown compounds were synthesized in ~70% yield by the reactions of [Cr(L)₂PyCl]Cl₂.H₂O (13) with acetylacetone, glycine, *N*-phenylsalicylaldehyde and *N*-phenylortho-hydroxyacetophenoneimine (1 : 1) respectively, in ethanol under reflux. The filtrate from 21 afforded another red-brown heterochelate of chromium(III) involving acetylacetonate anion and the dianion of the Schiff base *N,N'*-1,3-propane-2-ol-bis(acetylacetonimine), [(acac)Cr-(acacpnol)] (25) in about 15% yield.

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